

How did the Inka Calculate?

The Yupana, a Mysterious Peruvian Abacus

Unlike the Chinese, Japanese and Russian bead frames, the Peruvian abacus is unknown even to many experts. Despite decades of research, it is still unclear how the Inka used this enigmatic digital calculating device. This is because there are hardly any contemporary descriptions. In addition, the abacus mentioned in the literature differs greatly from the finds made in Peru and Ecuador. In contrast to the knotted cords (quipus), which were used to store the results, only a few yupanas have survived. According to another interpretation, these mysterious objects were even models for urban planning.

By Herbert Bruderer

The most common bead frames include Chinese, Japanese, and Russian abacuses as well as school abacuses. Less well known is the Roman hand abacus, of which only three original pieces have survived, and the mysterious Inka counting board, the Yupana. The Inka used knotted cords (quipus or khipus) to store numerical values and Yupanas for calculations. While several hundred knotted cords have been preserved, only a few archaeological Yupanas have survived. The word yupay, which comes from the Quechua language, means “count”. The mostly square or rectangular boards were made of wood, stone or clay. They consisted of several compartments on different levels. Calculations were made with pebbles or seeds. Little is known about this device from contemporary literature (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. This image from Felipe Guamán Poma de Ayala: *El primer nueva corónica y buen gobierno* (1615) shows a person with a knotted cord and (bottom left) a yupana with five rows and four columns. The book is located in Copenhagen, Credit: Royal Danish Library, Copenhagen.

There are two forms of the yupana: the literary yupana, i.e. the model according to Guamán Poma de Ayala, and the archaeological yupana (table yupana). As far as we know, the first archaeological yupana was found in Chordeleg (Ecuador) in 1869. It is made of wood. In 1878, a specimen appeared in Caraz, Peru. The archaeological yupana has quite different shapes, which is rather unusual for a calculating aid. Yupanas may

not only have been mathematical devices, they may also have served as architectural models for urban planning or as game boards (see Figure 2). They are also reminiscent of tectonic puzzle grids.

Figure 2. City floor plan (model), Credit: Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Ethnografisches Museum / Ines Seibt [CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/)

How do you calculate with the Peruvian abacus?

To this day it is unknown how the Inka worked with these calculators. There are numerous hypotheses about their use, e.g. by Henry Wassén (1931), Carlos Radicati di Primeglio (1951 and 1976), William Burns Glynn (1981), Martha Villavicencio Ubillús (1982), Carlos Alberto Hernández García (1986), Juan Ansión (1990), Hugo Pereyra Sánchez (1990), Oscar Pacheco Ríos (1999), Nicolino de Pasquale (2001), Viviana Moscovich (2007), Cinzia Florio (2008), Rodrigo Rivas Oré (2009), Andrés Chirinos Rivera (2010), Miguel Ángel Pinto Tapia (2010), Jesús Ríos Mencia (2012), Dhavit Prem (2014), Ángel Bernabé Palli Salas (2015) and Herbert Jhon Apaza Luque (2017). The Inka used the decimal place-value system. They knew the number zero and perhaps also the Fibonacci sequence.

A good overview of the various attempts at explanation can be found in Henry-Mark Vilca-Apaza et al.: *Yupana o ábaco inca, a 100 años (1912-2022): experiencias y posibilidades de educación matemática en América Latina*, also in Henry-Mark Vilca-Apaza et al.: *La Yupana o ábaco peruano y el aprendizaje de la matemática: de lo concreto a lo abstracto, de la escuela a la universidad*. Similarly Raúl Ibáñez in *Quipu y yupana, instrumentos matemáticos incas (II)*, Molly Leonard et al.: *The Incan Abacus: A Curious Counting Device*, and Cinzia Florio: *Encuentros y Desencuentros en la identificación de una relación matemática en la yupana de Guaman Poma de Ayala*. However, most of the theories only concern the literary Yupana.

A comprehensive presentation of the different hypotheses with instructions for use can be found in Mamani Zevallos: *La Yupana en el aprendizaje de la matemática*. Further instructions come from Ximena Catepillán et al.: *Counting and Arithmetic of the Inca* and Costanza Bustos et al.: *El ábaco inca y las operaciones aritméticas*. Probably the most comprehensive work on the various suggestions (with examples for the four basic arithmetic operations as well as for exponentiation and root extraction) is provided by Dhavit Prem. *Hatun Yupana Qellqa. Decodificando la Matemática Inka*.

Examples of the four basic arithmetic operations can be found in Viviana Ruth Moscovich: *Yupana, tabla de contar inca: Estructura interna*, Viviana Ruth Moscovich: *El Khipu y la Yupana. Administración y Contabilidad en el Imperio Inca*, Andrés Chirinos Rivera: *Quipus del Tahuantinsuyo*, Rossmary Juana Silvina Zevallos Mamani: *La Yupana en el aprendizaje de la matemática* and (also for exponentiation and root extraction) in Henry-Mark Vilca-Apaza et al.: *La Yupana o ábaco peruano y el aprendizaje de la matemática: de lo concreto a lo abstracto, de la escuela a la universidad*.

Dhavit Prem provides a very helpful overview of different methods (see Table 1).

Table 1: List of suggested solutions. Source: Dhavit Prem: Hatun Yupana Qellqa. Decodificando la Matemática Inka, page 14

Autor	Nombre referencial	Procesamiento	Base num.	Sentido yupana	Req. orificios	2 Manos	Año
Henry Wassen	Método Wassen	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	Si	No	1931
Carlos Radicati Di Primeglio	Método Radicati Di Primeglio	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	No	No	1976
William Burns Glynn	Método William Burns	Indo - arábigo	10	Horizontal	Si	No	1981
Carlos Hernandez	Yupana Dinámica	Indo - arábigo	10	Horizontal	No	No	1986
Hugo Pereyra	Método Pereyra	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	No	No	1990
Juan Ansión	Método Ansión	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	Si	No	1990
Nicolino De Pasquale	Método De Pasquale	Indo - arábigo	40	Vertical	Si	No	2000
Andrés Chirinos	Método Chirinos	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	Si	No	2008
Cinzia Florio	Método Florio	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	No	No	2008
Rodrigo Rivas Oré	Método Yupana Kipu-ayuda	Indo - arábigo	10	Horizontal	Si	No	2009
Viviana Moscovich	Yupana, tabla de contar inca	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical en espejo	Si	No	2010
Comunidad Samsa	Método Samsa	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	Si	No	2012
Jesús Ríos Mencia	Yupana Ancestral	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	Si	No	2012
Nicolino De Pasquale	Decimal Guaman Poma	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	Si	No	2012
Anónimo "freejutube"	"Híbrido" Y. Dinámica - Pereira c/variantes	Indo - arábigo	10	Vertical	No	No	2013
Dhavit Prem	Tawa Pukllay - P'away Yupana	Formas y movimientos	10	Vertical	No	Si	2014
Dhavit Prem	Tawa Pukllay QOKA - para invidentes	Formas y movimientos	10	Vertical	No	Si	2014
Dhavit Prem (Dharma Jiten)	Método Tawa Pukllay	Formas y movimientos	10	Vertical	No	Si	2014

This is what Felipe Guamán Poma de Ayala's template looks like (see Figure 3)

Figure 3. Representation by Felipe Guamán Poma de Ayala, source: Cinzia Florio. *Encuentros y Desencuentros en la identificación de una relación matemática en la yupana de Guaman Poma de Ayala*, page 23.

A few suggested solutions follow (see Figures 4–10). Please refer to the specialist literature for more detailed information and how to calculate with these models.

Figure 4. Interpretation by Henry Wassén (1931), source: Cinzia Florio. *Encuentros y Desencuentros en la identificación de una relación matemática en la yupana de Guaman Poma de Ayala*, page 8.

Figure 5. Interpretation by Carlos Radicati di Primeglio (1951), source: Cinzia Florio. *Encuentros y Desencuentros en la identificación de una relación matemática en la yupana de Guaman Poma de Ayala*, page 9.

Figure 6. Interpretation by William Burns Glynn (1981), source: Rossmary Juana Silvina Zevallos Mamani. *La Yupana en el aprendizaje de la matemática*, page 55.

Figure 7. Interpretation by Nicolino de Pasquale (2001), source: Cinzia Florio. *Encuentros y Desencuentros en la identificación de una relación matemática en la yupana de Guaman Poma de Ayala*, page 10.

Figure 8. Interpretation by Viviana Moscovich (2007), source: Viviana Ruth Moscovich. *El Khipu y la Yupana. Administración y Contabilidad en el Imperio Inca*, page 169.

Figure 9. Interpretation by Cinzia Florio (2008), source: Cinzia Florio. *Encuentros y Desencuentros en la identificación de una relación matemática en la yupana de Guaman Poma de Ayala*, page 15.

Figure 10. Interpretation by Andrés Chirinos Rivera (2010), source: Andrés Chirinos Rivera. *Quipus del Tahuantinsuyo. Curacas, Incas y su saber matemático en el siglo XVI*, page 182.

According to Dhavit Prem's model, the numbers 0 to 9 can be represented as follows (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Representation of the numbers 0 to 9, source: Dhavit Prem. *Yupana Inka. Decoding Inka's Math. Tawa Pukllay Method*, page 23.

The value 15204 therefore looks as follows (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Representation of the number 15204, source: Dhavit Prem. *Hatun Yupana Qellqa. Decodificando la Matemática Inka*, page 65.

Prem's Awaqo Andino has this form (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. The Awaqo Andino, source: Dhavit Prem. *Hatun Yupana Qellqa. Decodificando la Matemática Inka*, page 132.

In the zero position, all beads are at the bottom (left), the number 3257 is set as follows (see Figure14).

Figure 14. The Awaqo Andino in basic position (left) and with the number 3257 (right), source: Dhavit Prem. *Hatun Yupana Qellqa. Decodificando la Matemática Inka*, page 133.

On the wooden European counting table and the decimal teaching abacus, the addition of two numbers works like this (see Figure 15). Subtraction is similar. Multiplication is a repeated addition, division is a successive subtraction.

Addition					
Units	Number-1	Number-2	Sum-1	Sum-2	Sum-2
10-000	●●	●●●●●	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●
1000	□	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●●●
100	●●●●●	●	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●
10	●●●●	●●●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●●●●●	●●●●	●●●●
1	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●	●●●●●●●●●●●●●●	●●●●	●●●●
□	20-537	48-196	□	68-733	68-733

Explanation of symbols
 ● = pebble
 ● = tens carry

Figure 15. Addition with tens transmission

There is an informative (speculative) video on how to operate the table yupana: [Inca Counting Boards \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...). (Mathispower4u, 2013)

This Peruvian abacus was divided into rectangular and square compartments according to the model by Lawrence Morales and David Lippmann (see Figure 16), leaving an octagonal field in the middle. Two opposite corners were significantly higher, the adjacent compartments slightly higher. This resulted in three levels. One pebble in the 12 square compartments represented the value 1. In the two rectangular compartments it had the value 2, in the octagonal field the value 3. A pebble in the middle level (two hexagonal compartments) counted 6-fold, in the top level (2 square compartments) 12-fold. Different objects could be identified by different colors. The calculation results (see Figures 17–18) were stored with the help of knotted cords (quipus).

For example, a pebble in a smaller (white) compartment represented one unit. Note that there are 12 such squares around the outer edge of the figure. If a pebble was put into one of the two (white) larger, rectangular compartments, its value was doubled. When a pebble was put in the octagonal region in the middle of the slab, its value was tripled. If a pebble was placed on the second (shaded) level, its value was multiplied by six. And finally, if a pebble was found on one of the two highest corner levels, its value was multiplied by twelve. Different objects could be counted at the same time by representing different objects by different colored pebbles.

Adapted from Math in Society by L. Morales/D. Lippman

Figure 16. Possible assignment of values in the Peruvian abacus. Source: [Inca Counting Boards \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)

Suppose a circle represents one dog and a square represents one goat. Determine the totals shown on the counting board.

$$(2 \times 12) + (2 \times 6) + (2 \times 3) + (3 \times 2) + (3 \times 1) = 24 + 12 + 6 + 6 + 3 = 51 \text{ dogs}$$

Adapted from Math in Society by L. Morales/D. Lippman

Figure 17. Example of an addition. A red circle represents a dog. Source: [Inca Counting Boards \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)

Figure 18. Example of an addition. A blue square represents a goat. Source: [Inca Counting Boards \(youtube.com\)](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)

In which collections are there yupanas?

The following are a few examples of yupanas that are in various museums. Information about other devices is welcome.

The Museo Larco in Lima has two pieces (see Figures 19–20).

Figure 19. Granite slab with two square platforms and a total of three levels, 200–600 AD, Credit: Museo Larco, Lima, Perú, ML301181

Figure 20. Rectangular stone slab with several levels, 200–600 AD, Credit: Museo Larco, Lima, Perú, ML301304

The stone tablet of the Museo de Arte de Lima (Mali), Peru (see Figures 21–22), was made between 1400 and 1532 AD.

Figure 21. Stone counting aid with several levels, Credit: Museo de Arte de Lima (Mali), Peru, Donación Memoria Prado

Figure 22. Yupana from above, Credit: Museo de Arte de Lima (Mali), Peru, Donación Memoria Prado

Another model is also located in Lima (see Figure 23).

Figure 23. Yupana from Callejón de Huaylas (Peru), made of carved stone (1400–1532 AD), with square and rectangular compartments distributed symmetrically to the axis, Credit: Museo Nacional de Arqueología, Antropología e Historia de Perú, Lima, Photo: Daniel Giannoni

In New York there is this stone sculpture (see Figure 24).

Figure 24. Stone sculpture from Peru (200–600 AD), Credit: American Museum of Natural History, New York

Yupanas also appear in European collections, for example in Milan (see Figures 25–26).

Figure 25. Yupana, pre-Spanish abacus, Chimù/Inca(?) culture, Peru, xv/ xvi century, wood. Federico Balzarotti collection, courtesy Comune di Milano, Mudec – Museo delle Culture- picture Studio Neon, *all rights reserved*, inv. PAM 01349

Figure 26. Yupana, pre-Spanish abacus, Chimù/Inca(?) culture, Peru, xv/xvi century, wood. Federico Balzarotti collection, courtesy Comune di Milano, Mudec – Museo delle Culture- picture Studio Neon, *all rights reserved*. inv. PAM 01364

The Musée du quai Branly – Jacques Chirac in Paris keeps two plaster casts (see Figures 27–28).

Figure 27. Plaster cast of a stone yupana, dated to 1450–1532 AD, Credit: Musée du quai Branly – Jacques Chirac, Paris

Figure 28. Plaster cast of a yupana, dated to the period 1450–1532 AD, Credit: Musée du quai Branly – Jacques Chirac, Paris

The following illustrations show objects found in Peru and Ecuador (see Figures 29-36).

Figure 29. Yupana made of stone from Ancash (Peru), Colección Radicati, source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu, Lima 1976

Figure 30. Yupana made of wood from Chan-Chan (Trujillo, Peru), source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu, Lima 1976

Figure 31. Yupana made of stone from Huancarcuchu (Ecuador), source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu, Lima 1976

Figure 32. Yupana made of sperm whale bone from Carhua (Pisco, Peru), Credit: Museo Regional de Ica, source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu, Lima 1976

Figure 33. Yupana made of sperm whale bone from Cárhua (Pisco, Peru), Credit: Museo Regional de Ica, source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: *El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu*, Lima 1976

Figure 34. Yupana made of sperm whale bone from Cárhua (Pisco, Peru), Credit: Museo Regional de Ica, source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: *El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu*, Lima 1976

Figure 35. Yupana clay platform fixed to the ground from Huacones-Cañete (Peru), source: Henry-Mark Vilca-Apaza et al: *Yupana o ábaco inca, a 100 años (1912-2022): experiencias y posibilidades de educación matemática en América Latina*, 2023, page 87

Figure 36. Depiction on a jug in which one of the people is carrying a board with squares, Credit: Museo Nacional de Arqueología, Antropología e Historia de Perú, Lima, source: Carlos Radicati di Primeglio: *El sistema contable de los Incas. Yupana y quipu*, Lima 1976

Conclusion

The mysterious yupana is a fascinating historical calculating aid of the Inka. In contrast to the Chinese, Japanese, Russian and Roman abacus, this counting board is hardly known even to experts. There are only a few contemporary descriptions of this device. It is still unclear how it was used. There are numerous theories about its use. Sometimes the archaeological yupana is interpreted as a model for city layouts.

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Note

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